

RETHINKING ROMANIA'S ROAD FREIGHT EMISSIONS FROM A SUSTAINABILITY CONTEXT

Corina CRUCERU ¹, Ionut NATEA ², Danut DUMITRASCU ³

PhD Student¹, PhD Student², Prof.³

University Lucian Blaga Sibiu

Bulevardul Victoriei 10, Sibiu 550024, România

corina.cruceru@ymail.com ¹, ionutdragos.natea@ulbsibiu.ro ², dan.dumitrascu@ulbsibiu.ro ³

<http://www.ulbsibiu.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose: *This study estimates Romania's road freight transport emissions and explores the efforts of managing these.*

Methodology/approach: *By examining key themes —such as energy transition, technological solutions, and climate change regulations—through a bibliometric analysis the study sheds light on Romania's role in the European road freight transportation landscape.*

Findings: *Despite efforts outlined in national programs, challenges persist, including data limitations. The findings show Romania's overall emissions falling, putting the country apparently on track for net zero, but transport emissions have been rising over the last decades.*

Research implications: *This underscores the importance of continued investment in infrastructure, adoption of cleaner technologies, and policy initiatives to achieve meaningful emissions reductions.*

Practical implications: *Ultimately, the study highlights the need for sustained efforts to achieve environmental sustainability in Romania's road freight sector.*

Originality/value: *This study fills a crucial gap in the literature, providing valuable insights on the Romanian road freight transport within the European context.*

Key words: *Road freight transport, emissions, Romania, decarbonization strategies, bibliometric analysis, sustainability.*

Introduction

Global road transport emissions account for about one-fifth of global CO₂ emissions. Passenger vehicles, including cars and buses, contribute around 45.1% of these emissions, while trucks carrying freight contribute approximately 29.4% (Ritchie, 2020). The rise in tailpipe CO₂ emissions from heavy-duty vehicles, especially trucks, since 2000, accounts for over 80% of this increase (IEA, 2024). Addressing emissions from this sector is crucial for global climate change mitigation efforts.

Numerous strategies and frameworks aim to decarbonize road freight transportation through technological innovations and operational measures (Meyer, 2020). However, research often focuses on specific areas, lacking a comprehensive view, especially on regional aspects. To fill this research gap and assess green road freight transportation, this paper uses bibliometric and network analysis for a comprehensive literature overview. This study uniquely examines Romania's road freight transportation decarbonization using a replicable, scientific, data-driven

review approach. It employs cocitation analysis to identify and cluster research streams. Following the research target of "Assessing and Managing Romania's road freight transport emissions," the paper addresses these research questions:

1. How has Romania's road freight transportation progressed over time in the European context, and what is its current emission level?
2. What specific challenges and measures are taken in Romania concerning road freight transport decarbonization?

After a literature review on road freight decarbonization, the paper captures specific data on Romania's road freight and analyzes decarbonization measures. It concludes with a discussion summarizing contributions and offering recommendations for future research.

Figure 1: Research Design

Road Freight Decarbonization Literature Review

A structured framework (Figure 2) helps understand the evolving landscape of sustainability research. This study, conducted January-May 2024, analyzes the current state, evolution, and management of sustainability in the road freight transport sector. Using bibliometric data and visualization tools like VOSviewer, we examine trends, influences, and interconnections in this multidisciplinary field. Network maps depicting keyword relationships provide insights into the intellectual structure of "decarbonization" up to early 2024.

The interdisciplinary nature of sustainability, spanning environmental science, economics, business, and social sciences, makes the Web of Science's (WoS) multidisciplinary coverage ideal for bibliometric analysis. To map the development of "Sustainability," we used WoS, filtering results in Management, Business, and Economics. We reviewed selected articles, focusing on abstracts and full texts, to examine road freight decarbonization and to explore the academic evolution of "transport sustainability" concepts. The bibliometric analysis, based on

the WoS Core Collection, retrieved 1799 publications on transport decarbonization, with less than 5% focused on road freight decarbonization.

Figure 2: Literature Review Structure

Figure 3 highlights core clusters of the selected articles:

- Energy Transition (red) requires meticulous planning to integrate various renewable sources into the energy system, with a focus on sector coupling, especially within transport. Advancements in smart grids and energy storage are essential for managing and utilizing renewable energy for transportation.
- Technological Solutions for Decarbonization
 - Electrification (purple) is a promising decarbonization pathway, leveraging renewable energy to charge batteries.
 - Hydrogen (green) particularly green hydrogen in the truck segment serves as a versatile energy carrier, with applications in fueling stations and grid stabilization.
- Climate Change Regulations and Energy Policies (light blue and yellow) to mitigate climate change requires effective prioritization and renewable energy. By aligning energy and transport policies and investing in infrastructure and technology, nations can significantly reduce emissions and foster sustainability.

The evolution of road freight decarbonization research has progressed from broad conceptualizations to detailed examinations of specific regions and technologies. Initially, studies such as "(Mattila & Antikainen, 2011) and "The long haul towards decarbonising road freight - A global assessment to 2050" (Mulhollanda, et al., 2017) set ambitious goals for emissions reduction. As research advanced, more focused analyses emerged, including investigations into national contexts like "Driving down road transport CO2 emissions in Scotland" (Melo, 2016). Furthermore, studies delved into specific technologies like electrification and alternative fuels, as seen in "Prospects for Electrification of Road Freight" (Nicolaidis, et al., 2018) and "Market diffusion of alternative fuels and powertrains in heavy-duty vehicles: A literature review" (Kluschke, et al., 2019). Overall, the evolution reflects a shift from broad objectives to nuanced approaches tailored to distinct contexts and technologies as

- Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure: Central to defining sustainability objectives in freight transport, it develops policies and strategies to promote energy-efficient transport, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and improve infrastructure.
- Ministry of Environment, Water, and Forests: Develops policies and strategies for environmental protection in freight transport, promotes less polluting transport modes to reduce environmental impacts.
- Romanian Road Authority (ARR): Regulates and supervises road transport, develops and implements regulations to reduce emissions, and improve commercial vehicle energy efficiency.
- National Agency for Environmental Protection (ANPM): Monitors and controls compliance with environmental protection laws in freight transport, contributes to defining sustainability objectives by monitoring and reporting emissions.

The Transport Programme (TP) 2021-2027 outlines Romania's "Vision for 2030," aiming for a high-quality transport infrastructure network that ensures connectivity within Romania and the EU, aligning with climate neutrality and environmental protection goals. Specific legislation targeting CO2 emissions in the truck or haulage sector is currently limited.

Figure 4: Road freight decarbonization articles as per Web of Science

Figure 5 encapsulates a comprehensive climate change mitigation approach, combining global agreements and regional policies with local and national implementation. International panels like the IPCC provide guidance, while regional alignments ensure consistency. National policies and laws, such as Legea 57/2012, support these efforts. The ultimate goal is global impact, including meeting the 1.5-degree Celsius target from agreements like the Paris Agreement and the Sustainable Development Goals. In line with other government programs, Romania's specific objectives include:

- Modernizing and expanding transport infrastructure.
- Improving connectivity of urban nodes to transport networks.
- Increasing rail transport market share
- Implementing traffic management and digitization systems to optimize flow.

- Maintaining road infrastructure to reduce congestion and accidents.
- Aligning with EU policies on sustainable, climate-friendly transport.

Figure 5: Top down climate change plans and bottom up coupling approaches

Romania's Emissions in the European Road Freight Transportation Context

The EU27's transportation infrastructure is notable for its extensive road network and efficient commercial freight operations. While it ranks third globally in motorways and paved roads after China and the US, the EU27 leads in commercial freight transport with 36.5 million commercial vehicles, surpassing China in operational capacity. Since 1995, the EU27's road freight transport has grown significantly from 1127.2 billion tkm to 1862.5 billion tkm in 2021, ranking third after China (6908.7 billion tkm) and the US (3129 billion tkm) (Commision, 2023).

The Romanian transport sector is a key component of the EU, employing about 383,400 individuals in 2020, or 2% of the country's population (Carlier, 2024). Romania ranks seventh among EU nations in transport industry employment and the number of enterprises. Road freight transport is crucial, particularly for international long-distance transport between third countries in the region. In 2021, Romania recorded 20.5 billion tkm in national haulage and 41.4 billion tkm in international road haulage, considering only heavy goods vehicles (>3.5 tonnes load capacity). As of December 2022, Romania had 155,351 registered HDTs over 3.5 tonnes, with majority of 154,700 being diesel (Statista, 2023).

To estimate road freight transport emissions in Romania, we combine transport volume with average emissions per tonne-kilometre (tkm) based on European data. Although local road conditions and traffic impact emissions, these details are simplified for estimation purposes, based on following:

- Emission Function: $f(x)$ be the function calculating average CO₂ emissions of heavy-duty trucks in grams per tonne-kilometre (g/tkm) based on the truck's weight x in tonnes, where $3.5 < x < 40$ (Gesellschaft, 2024).
- Freight Transport Volume: In 2021, Romania's freight transport totaled 20.5 billion tkm national and 41.4 billion tkm international haulage, including cross-trade and cabotage.
- Emission Calculation: Total CO₂ emissions for national and international haulage are calculated by multiplying emissions per tkm by the sum of haulage

Based on these inputs estimated emissions reach ~5.3Mt CO₂e in 2021. For comparison, Romania's total transport emissions in 2020 were 18.2Mt CO₂e, with transport being the second-largest emissions source after energy and heat, which emitted 22.04Mt CO₂e (Ritchie, Our World in Data, 2023). In 2021, total transport emissions reached 19Mt CO₂e, with road transport accounting for over 90%. Consequently, road freight transport emissions constituted 26% of Romania's transport emissions and 4.5% of the country's total emissions in 2021, a significant proportion compared to other European countries, highlighting Romania's crucial role in the European logistics network.

Figure 6: Romania's Emissions as total and transport GHG emissions

Findings & Limitations

With over 5Mt CO₂e estimated for road freight transport in 2022, the road freight transport represents a significant contributor to greenhouse gas emissions specifically for Romania. As a primary freight transport mode road freight vehicles heavily relies on fossil fuels representing Romanias second biggest oil consummator. Given the reforms initiated, the targets set in the programmes analysed seem to be in line with EUs ambitious CO₂ standards - aiming for 90% emissions reduction by 2040 most new trucks and coaches- and reflecting a comprehensive decarbonization approach clustered into:

1. *Energy Transition* (IMF, 2023): Romania is making significant strides towards an energy transition, boasting a renewable energy share of 23.6% in 2021, surpassing the EU average. This transition is evident in the shift towards low-carbon electricity generation, with hydro, biomass, nuclear, wind, and solar sources comprising 64% of Romania's electricity mix. However, challenges persist, particularly in the transport sector, where high oil dependency

fuels a continuous rise in emissions. Emissions in this sector are projected to surge by 84% by 2030, exacerbating the divergence from the EU's downward emission trend.

2. *Technological solutions* for decarbonization electrification and green for hydrogen are available yet not readily applicable and depend highly on infrastructure. Adoption of electric vehicles remains low, necessitating further investments in charging infrastructure and incentives such as 'Rabla Plus Program'. Energy efficiency measures for road freight include aerodynamics, low rolling resistance (LRR), tyres/Tyre pressure systems (TPS) as well as light-weighting assuming as per (Mulholland, et al., 2017) that "all HDV vehicle types -except utility trucks- could cost effectively reduce weight >7% within the next ten years" or intramodal transportation as suggested by (Kaack, et al., 2018)

3. *Climate regulations* progress towards EU's Fit-for-55 target, with current emissions relatively low even projected to exceed the 55% reduction target before 2030 (IMF, 2023). Achieving the longer-term net-zero target by 2050 is uncertain despite EURO-VI&EURO-VII strict emission limits (Climate, 2024) (Comission, 2024). Despite decarbonization efforts, Romania's energy and emission intensity remain high, and while the transport sector is diverging from the EU's declining trajectory, demanding a transition towards greater electric mobility fueled by renewable energy sources might pose several challenges, ranging from social-technical (energy transition) to economical (return on investments) and environmental (emission measurement) which per (Neagoe, et al., 2024) seem unlikely to be resolved in near future.

Overall emissions in this study have been constrained by insufficient data, high-level statistical estimation based import and export haulage activities. Figures for road freight vehicle emissions base on CO₂ averages obviously omitting other harmful pollutants such as nitrogen oxides for simplification purposes. Further studies could focus on a detailed modelling with comprehensive and accurate dataset.

Discussion & conclusions

Road freight transport in the EU27 is integral to the region's economy representing a major primary energy consumer e.g. 2015 road freight oil consumption required 18 % of the total energy and European road freight activities have nearly quadrupled during the last 3 decades (IEA, 2017). Despite challenges posed by environmental pollution, policy efforts and operational efficiency have contributed to progress in emissions reduction and environmental sustainability. Moving forward, continued investment in infrastructure, adoption of cleaner technologies, and policy initiatives will be essential to ensure the continued efficiency and sustainability of road freight transport in the EU27 as e.g. lately approved a 60.7 million euro scheme to support haulage and bus companies in the country within the context of 'Russia's war on Ukraine.

Considering the coupling of economic growth and road freight carbon emissions achieving tkm reduction seems exceedingly challenging, therefore efforts to decarbonize need to concentrate on decreasing carbon intensity of freight transport to a fraction of its present level (McKinnon, 2016). Global assessments indicate 56% increase in road freight GHGs between 2015 and 2050 in face of limited prospects of maximum potential reduction over the same timeframe which was found to be 60% (Mulholland, Teterb, Cazzolab, McDonald, & Gallachóira, 2017).

Overall, while global road transport emissions present a significant challenge in the fight against climate change, there is growing momentum and commitment from various stakeholders to address this issue. Continued collaboration, innovation, and policy support will be essential in driving meaningful reductions in emissions from road transport worldwide. There are promising developments show countries and regions implementing ambitious

policies and initiatives to promote the adoption of electric vehicles and reduce emissions from road transport, but these efforts need financial incentives and proper infrastructure.

Despite the widespread acknowledgment of the environmental impact of road transport emissions, significant challenges remain in reducing these in Romania. The steady increase in transportation demand, coupled with economic expansion, poses challenges to achieving substantial reductions. Moreover, the transition to cleaner technologies and alternative fuels faces barriers such as infrastructure limitations, cost considerations, and consumer preferences.

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